

Introducing RAS Lab a new experimental facility

Vasco Mota, PhD
Research Scientist

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Recirculating aquaculture systems

What are RAS?

Recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) *or closed containment systems (CCS)*

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(shell) fish production units that treat and re-use water

Series
for aquaculture III
original in
the water after
breeding and for

Recirculating aquaculture systems

What are RAS?

Recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) *or closed containment systems (CCS)*

(shell) fish production units that treat and re-use water

Two distinctive characteristics:

- **Water exchange rate:** water re-use > 90%, nitrate (NO_3) is the controlling parameter.
- **Water treatment units:** mechanical filtration (solids), biofiltration ($\text{NH}_3/\text{NH}_4^+$, NO_2), gas exchange (CO_2)

RASLab: 9 experimental RAS units

Where?

Havbruksstasjonen i Tromsø AS
Skarsfjordvegen 860, 9131 Kårvika

RASLab: 9 experimental RAS units

Where?

Fish Health lab (Fiskehelselaboratoriet)

- Approved for experiments on several fish diseases and GMO
- Waste water treatment is heated (81 ° C for 19 minutes) to eliminate the pathogens

RASLab: 9 experimental RAS units

Why?

- **Challenge trials.** Test disinfection strategies for fish and system treatment units
- **Flexibility.** modular construction allows testing new units
- **Low operating costs.** reduced water use

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Why?

- **Challenge trials.** Test disinfection strategies for fish and system treatment units
- **Flexibility.** modular construction allows testing new units
- **Low operating costs.** reduced water use
- **Increase collaboration.** Attract scientists for projects in this unique facility
- **Training.** HiT, UiT and Nofima staff can be trained in these lab-scale systems
- **Teaching.** Practical classes/thesis for BSc and MSc students
- **High scientific output.** Controlled conditions and replication

RASLab: 9 experimental RAS units

Who?

Winner of international tender competition

- Experience in design and installing experimental RAS

RASLab: 9 experimental RAS units

What?

#	Item Name	Area	Description	Specifications	Qty	Unit / Meas
1	Tanks	RAS	AquaCirc custom made tanks (0.5m ²)	500L round tanks with base, connection ports and sloped bottom	9	P
2	Tank Lids		AquaCirc Custom made tank lid	Full tank lid with splash protection	9	P
3	Pipe work		AquaCirc Valves, pipes, gates, joints, connections		9	P
4	Drum filter		AquaCirc DF-T1	5 m ³ /h, 40 micron mesh	9	P
5	Backwash pump		AquaCirc D50T	0.4L/s at 6 bar, 0.6 m ³ /h @ 68.5m head	9	P
6	Backwash Pump Prefilter		AquaCirc Prefilter (Y-type)	Protection for drum filter spray nozzles	9	P
7	Pump Stand + DF Stand		AquaCirc GRP Items	GRP Pump Stand + DF Stand	9	P
8	Aeration grids		AquaCirc - Medium pore diffusion	Perfortated hose for Oxygenation, degassing & moving bed biofilter	9	P
9	Biofilter Tank		AquaCirc Biofilter sump (0.40m ³)	400L GRP Custom made sump with divider and mesh	9	P
10	Biomedia		AquaCirc Biomedia	900m ² /m ³ Biomedia , low head loss type for efficient moving bed	1	m ³
11	Pump		AquaCirc Main flow pumps 320W	Rated for seawater, 5m ³ /h @ 5m head - Inverter technology Max 320W	9	P
12	Degassing unit		AquaCirc - PS3 - 3,000 L/h each unit	3m ³ /hr to work with SW/FW	9	P
13	P.skimmer Solenoid Valve		AquaCirc - Auto wash down	Foam Backwashing Solenoid with Timer	9	P
14	Saturation cones		AquaCirc Oxygen/Ozone Cones - OCB	8m ³ / hr - 0.6 Bar operating pressure	9	P
15	Heat pump		AquaCirc TK1000	Min. 0.5-0.8m ³ /h	9	P
16	Pressure Gauge		AquaCirc Pressure Gauge	0-3 Bar Gauge	18	P
17	Emergency Oxygen		AquaCirc Emergency O ₂ line with diffusers	Oxygen diffusers and fittings	9	P
#	Item Name	Area	Description	Specifications	Qty	Unit / Meas
18	Water meter counter	Inlet	AquaCirc water meter	Max operating pressure 16 bar, 2.5m ³ /h	18	P
#	Item Name	Area	Description	Specifications	Qty	Unit / Meas
19	Monitoring System	Monitoring	AquaCirc Monitoring & Control System	DO, pH, Level sensors, data logging	1	P
20	Oxygen Dosing Cabinets		AquaCirc Monitoring & Control System	Staged solenoids + interface for flow control - Oxygen rated, Ozone flow meters	1	P
21	Emergency Oxygen Cabinets		AquaCirc Monitoring & Control System	Staged solenoids + interface for flow control - Oxygen rated	1	P
#	Item Name	Area	Description	Specifications	Qty	Unit / Meas
22	Technical Support	Support	Remote and online support	One year period	1	P

RASLab: 9 experimental RAS units

What?

Equipment: Required: nine (9) independent and identical RAS units

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Equipment: Required: nine (9) independent and identical RAS units *each* consisting of:

1. Fish tank 500L
2. Mechanical filtration unit – drum filter
3. Biological unit – Moving bed biofilm reactor (MBBR)
4. Gas exchange unit – degasser
5. Oxygenation – oxygen cone

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4. Gas exchange unit – degasser
5. Oxygenation – oxygen cone
6. Temperature control unit – heating and cooling
7. Water flow control unit
8. Water flow meter
9. Oxygen, Ph, temperature and water level sensors and monitoring system
10. Pump

Figure 1 General view of system 1

RASLab: 9 experimental RAS units

What?

Equipment requirements and details:

General characteristics		
Salinity range	0 - 34	ppt
Temperature range	8 - 14	°C
Primary fish species	Atlantic salmon parr, smolts and post-smolts	
Fish size range	10 - 500	g
Max. biomass	50	kg
Max. feed load	1	Kg/day
Protein content feed	50	%

Transformation process

★ UTGANG

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Neuderman

830

Pacific

DOSE S1-3

DOSE S4-6

DOSE S7-9

09:24:58

PID Cone S1 0%	PID Cone S2 0%	PID Cone S3 0%	PID Cone S4 0%	PID Cone S5 0%	PID Cone S6 0%	PID Cone S7 4.4%	PID Cone S8 0%	PID Cone S9 0%
Reg Em. Dos S1 Inactive	Reg Em. Dos S2 Inactive	Reg Em. Dos S3 Inactive	Reg Em. Dos S4 Inactive	Reg Em. Dos S5 Inactive	Reg Em. Dos S6 Inactive	Reg Em. Dos S7 Inactive	Reg Em. Dos S8 Inactive	Reg Em. Dos S9 Inactive

S1-3

S4-6

S7-9

DO-S1 93.8 %	DO-S2 94.7 %	DO-S3 91.0 %	DO-S4 95.7 %	DO-S5 93.9 %	DO-S6 92.9 %	DO-S7 89.3 %	DO-S8 91.7 %	DO-S9 93.2 %
pH S1 7.89 pH	pH S2 7.63 pH	pH S3 7.61 pH	pH S4 7.94 pH	pH S5 7.91 pH	pH S6 7.84 pH	pH S7 7.85 pH	pH S8 7.66 pH	pH S9 7.82 pH

AQUA BIOTECH GROUP

Intense ongoing research activity

+ 5 projects

+ 6 MSc thesis

+ 10 Nofima and UiT researchers/technicians

Example of ongoing and planned work

Determination of the **peracetic acid exposure concentration and administration** method without effect on Atlantic salmon **parr** (*Salmo salar*) health, welfare or growth

Test the effects of different dietary protein:energy ratios on **smoltification and on post-smolt robustness**

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Determination of the **peracetic acid exposure concentration and administration** method without effect on Atlantic salmon **parr** (*Salmo salar*) health, welfare or growth

Test the effects of different dietary protein:energy ratios on **smoltification and on post-smolt robustness**

To evaluate how different vectors influence the **persistence of the pathogens in a FW-RAS**

Benchmark study on **peracetic acid and ozone administration** to control a *Y. ruckeri* outbreak in Atlantic salmon parr freshwater-RAS and fish welfare indicators assessment

Pilot-study on the combination of **UV irradiation and peracetic acid potential to inactivate pathogens in RAS**

There were so many people involved to acknowledge, but special credit to:

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Salo

**HAVBRUKS-
STASJONEN**
I T R O M S Ø

Thank you for your attention! Questions?

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